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ABSTRACTS

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Jaggery-assisted, cost-effective textile dye treatment through RSM optimization: Eco-friendly approach

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Abstract: Due to the increasing population, the demand for the textile sector has increased in the past few years, causing water pollution a burning issue. Textile industries primarily treat wastewater generated from their various units. Later, the common effluent treatment plant treats it by primary, secondary, and tertiary treatment and tries to meet the effluent discharge limits set by the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB), before discharging the water into the environment. In previous years synthetic media like yeast extract, peptone, and glucose were used for dye degradation at the laboratory scale, which drawbacks strong odour and gas formation. To overcome these issues, we are currently working on improving biological treatment by using black jaggery as the sole carbon and nitrogen source. The Optimization of jaggery concentration, inoculum volume and dye concentration were optimized with the help of Response Surface Methodology (RSM). The azo dyes mainly break down in anaerobic conditions and formed aromatic amines require aerobic conditions for further mineralization to overcome this situation a Sequencing batch reactor (SBR) is operated in aerobic /anaerobic cycles for complete degradation of dyes using jaggery as a nutrient supplement.

Keywords- *Textile industry, effluent, decolourisation, azo dye, synthetic media, jaggery, sequencing batch reactor.*

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